

TECHNOLOGIES FOR ORGANIZING CLASSES USING INTERACTIVE TECHNIQUES IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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Annotation: in this article, the interest of the generation in learning foreign languages is growing. Therefore, the teaching of a foreign language, including English, in secondary schools requires the use of interactive methods in classes. This article is devoted to the effects of organizing classes using interactive techniques in English classes of secondary schools.

Keywords: method, interactive method, information and Communication Technology, interoperability.

In our country, significant work is being carried out on the formation of an information society, the introduction of the most advanced information and communication technologies in all areas. In particular, the capabilities of Interactive (Interactive) Services are highly valued in this process. The Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language describes the concept of "interactive" as based on the reception or transmission of information through a computer network. In Wikipedia, however, interactivity has been evaluated as a concept that reveals the character and level of reciprocal motion between objects, with applications in information theory, Informatics and programming, telecommunication systems, sociology, industrial design, etc. In a word, interactivity is a system of organization, which is the achievement of a certain goal by establishing the exchange of information between parts of the ridge. Interactive method-serves to activate the acquisition of knowledge by students, to develop their personal qualities by increasing the activity between students and the teacher in the educational process. The use of interactive techniques will help increase the effectiveness of the lesson. The main criteria for interactive education are: the opportunity to conduct informal discussions, freely state and express educational material, the low number of lectures, but the large number of seminars, the creation of opportunities for students to take initiatives, the assignment of tasks to work as a small group, a large group, a class team, the performance of written works and other methods. Currently, one of the main directions in the field of improving educational methods is the introduction of interactive educational and educational methods. All science teachers are increasingly using interactive methods in the course of classes. As a result of the application of interactive methods, students' skills to independently think, analyze, draw conclusions, state their own opinion, be able to defend it on the basis of it, conduct healthy communication, discussion, debate are formed and develop. In the process of interactive education, the lesson is carried out on the basis of interaction of students.

Interactive methods, which are considered modern in the methodology of teaching a foreign language, were developed by scientists and proved them to have a greater level of efficiency compared to traditional methods. Interactive methods greatly increase the cognitive potential of the educational process compared to traditional methods. Because, in interactive methods, the student himself thinks freely independently, works as a partner with the teacher. As a foreign language is taught through modern technologies, in which the student himself plans the

course process, deals with it on the basis of the curriculum set by him, the teaching methods are selected by the student and the teacher in cooperation, participate in the discussion of educational material. In this, students help each other.

In the field of education in the late 20th and early 21st centuries, the term "interactive" methods is widely used in pedagogical literature. We will try to reveal the essence of this phrase. "Inter" continues to be used in the sense of acute. Interactive means an extremely active method of Education. This group of methods ensures that effective exposure in the quick term allows students to think independently, to be interested in creativity and the essence of the topic in them. From traditional methods of teaching, such as interactive methods, explanation, instruction and the use of tools, its effectiveness is high, which is an important factor in the formation of students as individuals, increasing their private abilities, ensuring their creative independence.

The differences between interactive education and traditional education can be seen in:

1. When teaching subjects in the curriculum, it is necessary to take into account which topics it is advisable to organize interactive lessons. This involves the use of interactive or traditional types of training, which ensure the full achievement of the goal of training on each topic.
2. In order for an interactive session to be effective, it is necessary to ensure that students know the basic concepts and preliminary information on its subject before the new session.
3. In an interactive session, it is necessary to take into account that in order for students to work independently, a lot of time is spent compared to a traditional one.

A few centuries ago about the impact of these similar differences in social life A. In the preface to his famous work "Mahbub ul-qulub", Navoi wrote: "Hope ulkim, readers will look at attention and attention, and each of them will be able to spring according to their understanding...". It shows that everyone can understand, assimilate, benefit and practice this work differently, that is, only at the level of their understanding, from which we can express our above conclusions about the main differences of interactive educational methods from traditional ones, which are more concise and consist in cultivating the perception of students' understanding.

It should be noted that the methods of interactive education have been used in Uzbekistan since ancient times in the educational process in such forms as discussion, discussion, negotiation, observation, analysis, consultation, consultation, mutolaa in the dialogue between the teacher and students and students. These techniques served to make students grow up to be independent-minded, perfect people by cultivating speech, reflection, meditation, mind, talent, intelligence. It is now known that when conducting interactive training, mainly interactive methods are used. And in the future, it is advisable that these methods will grow to a certain extent to interactive technology. This is an interactive method, and the difference between the concepts of technology can be described in our opinion as such. Interactive learning method-implemented by each teacher at the level of available tools and their own capabilities.

Interactive learning technology-ensures that each teacher conducts an activity that all students master as intended. In this, each student, having his own motives and intellectual level, masters the training to the extent foreseen. Based on the study of some experiments on the practical application of interactive training, we can indicate some factors that affect the quality and effectiveness of these training. They can be conditionally called organizational-pedagogical,

scientific-methodological and factors that depend on the teacher, students, means of Education. We must assume that they have a positive or negative effect in their essence.

There are many types of interactive training, which are selected and duly prepared in accordance with the features of the topic of the lesson as well as the intended goals. To participate in an interactive session, specific requirements are imposed on the readiness of students, which consist in mastering the necessary knowledge for active participation in the session, readiness for communication, working in cooperation, independent thinking, skills for FREE statement and protection of one's own opinion, etc. Making good use of time in training is a necessary condition. To do this, it is necessary to correctly select, prepare the necessary tools, and trainings and their tasks should be clearly defined.

In conclusion, the teacher, aiming to ensure the effectiveness of the lesson, achieves his goal only if he skillfully uses interactive lesson methods in his place.

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